

RECTIFYING THE ERRORS OF SECONDARY LEVEL STUDENTS IN LEARNING CONJUNCTIONS USING ANIMATED MOVIES

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Abstract:

The current paper attempts to rectify the conjunction error using animated movies. Grammar means the way words arranged and sentence formed. If the formation of sentence or word order changes the total concept will change. Grammar helps the person to convey their thoughts and ideas in right manner. Human thoughts, ideas and concepts are shared through language. Grammar is like a soul for the language. Grammar has certain rules and norms to use proper language. The breaking of rules and norms is also called as error. Error alone differs which is correct and incorrect. Errors alone help a person to correct the values of life. This paper also deals about error and how learners correct the error by themselves. Conjunction means connection. It connects words, phrases, sentences and paragraphs. It connects the complex structure for better understanding. This conjunction becomes a complication for many learners. Learners who are good in language also make error while using complex structure. This paper is an attempt to reduce their error with the help of technological aids. The approach used for this attempt is App assisted Language Learning. This approach is one of easiest and useful way for learners in pandemic situation.

Key Words: Conjunction error, animated movie, App Assisted Language Learning Approach.

1. Introduction:

English is a world-wide communicative language. It has a large exposure around the world. The significant part in language is Grammar. Grammar is like a base for the building. It gives structure to a language. The rules and forms present in grammar help to organise the language. The rules present in the grammar helps to construct a sentence. The constructed sentences help to transform a clear idea of others. Grammar constructs a way to use the word. The proper word usage in the proper sentence helps to deliver a great knowledge towards people. Grammar is more important for writing skill than speaking skill. There are lots of building in grammar. One of the important blocks in grammar is parts of speech. Each part plays a vital role to structure a sentence. In this paper, one of the important block conjunctions is discussed. Conjunction helps to relate words, phrases and clauses. It is very important to form a complex sentence. It avoids the multiple short sentences and avoids ambiguity in the complex sentence structure. There are three parts in conjunctions. They are coordinating conjunction, correlative conjunction and subordinating conjunction. The other significant part in this paper is Error. Error means the usage of wrong fact or idea. The deviation from rules and norms is also called as error. The person may convey their ideas in any form but error free language alone helps for better understanding. The major aim of this paper is to rectify or reduce the error of second language learners. This rectification helps to improve their writing skill and speaking skill.

2. Rectifying Conjunction Error through Animated Movies:

The present study aims to rectify the students' conjunction error through animated movies. App Assisted Language Learning Approach paves a way to reach the goal. Animated movies were used as a tool to rectify the students' conjunction error. Movies help to rectify the students' error in a simple and funny way. Nowadays, technology has become the tool for the study. Movies play an entertainer role in the life of students. Especially animated movies became as the medicine for all the mental pressure gone through during online classes and pandemic situation. In movies dialogues are the significant part to sort out their fallacy in language. Students pay attention towards the dialogues and it helps to rectify the error in a leisure way.

3. Purpose of the Study:

The purpose of the study is to rectify the path of students' language. Each and every student has a good knowledge to use language. Students are good in language but sometimes mistakes were made without their conscious. They didn't know what kinds of mistakes or error they did while using the language. Animated movies unconsciously rectify their error. The dialogues present in the movies unknowingly taught the students how to make construct a sentence in a right manner. The visual aids are more comical and play a role of stress buster. Students used for this study are secondary school students. They are more playful and they did not have

the peace of mind to accept or listen what others taught. But this is the age of the students must have to rectify their error or else the mistake will turn as a scar and remain till the end of their life. To remove the scar from their life this study is made by the researcher. This study not only rectifies the language but it also helps to improve their listening skills, creative skills and grammar skills. In this competitive world, error free language is significant. This method promotes the fun filled way of learning language in a precise manner. This method is suitable for contemporary period because it can be used in any place, anywhere and anytime.

4. Objectives:

- To rectify the conjunction error.
- It helps to construct a sentence structure.
- It improvises the language skill and listening skill.
- It also helps to learn grammar.
- To find the impact of students to rectify their error through animated movies.
- To improve the technological way of learning.

5. Approach:

The approach used for the study is App Assisted Language Learning Approach. Our contemporary world revolves around Apps. Apps become as air for humans. From the morning till night people use app for each and every purpose. In this pandemic situation, apps become as a survivor for humans. In pandemic period, students' towards education become as a question for parents. They became distant towards education. Apps had become as a survivor to connect student, teacher and education. Apps are not only used for education purpose but it also can use for business, marketing and other personal purpose. Our study uses both online and offline app for their learning. There are lots of software app helps to learn language and rectify the students' error. This approach deals with three elements:

- **Time:** Students can learn anytime. They did not have any time limit. Students can use their sufficient and convenient time to learn their language. Students can watch the selected animated movies in their convenient time.
- **Focus on Form:** Learners must have to focus on dialogues present in the movies. The sentence form and structure helps to rectify the students' conjunction error. Dialogues improvise their language skills and grammar skills.
- **Knowledge of Rules:** To rectify the mistake, learner must have the knowledge on grammar rules and forms. Apps make their understanding towards knowledge of rules in simple and easier way. It helps the learner to perform and rectify their error in language.

6. Identification of Problem:

This generation children do not have the broad mind to accept their mistakes pinpointed by others. They became very low if others try to rectify their error. Sometimes people are not ready to rectify the learners' error. Instead they mock on their errors. It made learners to develop inferiority complex towards language. This inferiority complex creates a burden to rectify their and learn language. Our current situation does not have the space to notice or rectify the students' error for teachers. Online classes concentrate on finishing the syllabus. The personal connection, notification and concern among students are disconnected in online classes. Learners started to make lots of error during this period. This present study takes an initial step to rectify conjunction error among learners. App Assisted Language Learning (Animated movies) was used to down their error and inferiority complex.

7. Methodology:

The researcher selected learners from secondary school. The researcher had a personal one to one conversation with students to break the alienated feeling and to know their language capacity. From this session, the researcher understood the difficulties in online classes and there capability towards technology. Researcher took the technological aid Movies app to taught students. The researcher also found that the students' are not able to identify what kind of mistakes they made while using the sentence. The pre-test were conducted for students to identify what kind of common errors made by the students. The tests were conducted with the help of Google forms. From the pre-test results, the researcher identified that the students felt very difficult to develop complex sentence structure and then they made the mistakes in conjunction. Conjunction helps to connect different sentences into one sentence. The researcher took a small step to rectify learners' conjunction error. For this rectification, researcher took the help of apps. Animated movies favour a lot for learners to understand the error. Nearly Ten animated movies were taken for this study. After each movie the test will be conducted through Google forms. The questions were based on conjunction from movies. The ten unit tests were conducted for learners. The researcher saw the improvement from the first test to tenth test. The researcher explains about conjunction and takes dialogues as examples from the movies to rectify the error. Learners showed the better improvement in the test. They unconsciously rectified their conjunction error while using language. The researcher shared some slides and explained to the students to differ the corrected and error sentence. Nearly thirty sessions were held between the researcher and learners. In the final session, the researcher conducted the post- test to identify whether this methodology may applicable for rectifying error.

8. Findings of the Study:

The researcher has selected two groups for the study. One is control group and the other one is experimental group. Both groups has been selected from the same school and class. The pre- test, unit test and post- test data were collected to analyse the methodology and approach.

Figure 1: Graphical representation of Post-Test Scores

The graphical representation shows the post-test scores (mean value) of control group and experimental group. The mean value of control group is 16.7 and the mean value of experimental group is 29.1. The difference between control group and experimental group is 12.4. From the analysis report, it found that the results are favouring towards experimental group.

9. Conclusion:

The aim of the research is to rectify the conjunction error through animated movies. From the results, it proves this approach helps to rectify the conjunction error among learners. It also improves the grammar skills and language skills. The mistakes must be rectified in the initial stage. Otherwise, the wound will develop as a cancer and destroy the body. Likewise, the mistakes must correct in initial stage or else it may destroy the language. This method develops learners individually as well as academically.

10. References:

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11. Appendix:

Apps Used

- You Tube
- Zoom App
- Whats App
- Website (Google Forms)

Movies Used

- The Little Mermaid
- Cinderella
- Peter Pan
- Tangled
- Frozen
- Frozen II
- Krishna
- Dragon
- Dragon II
- Aladdin